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D7.1 – Individual Exploitation Plans of Workbenches

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
BDI	Blue Data Infrastructures
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
KER	Key Exploitable Result
QC/QA	(Data) Quality Control / Quality Assessment
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
WB/s	Workbench/es
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Services
MEI	Marine Environmental Indicators
CORA	Coriolis Ocean Dataset for Reanalysis
NOAA	(US) National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
WOD	World Ocean Database
MSFD	(European) Marine Strategy Framework Directive
EEA	European Environmental Agency

Item	Description
UN SDG	United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
MOi	Mercator Ocean International
ODV	Ocean Data View

Keywords

EOSC; Workbench; EOVS; EBVS; data quality; workflows; exploitation; EDITO.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Essential Ocean Variables (EOV) and **Essential Biodiversity variables (EBV)** are critical for the analysis of the state of the environment and for numerical simulations, which can now be exposed to wider audiences and be used to accelerate Ocean knowledge and deepen our understanding of the trade-offs of human activities in the marine environment thanks to the potential brought by ongoing efforts to co-construct the **European Digital Twin Ocean (DTO)**. However, current data collections are based on a large number of data packages of different types and sources, computationally intensive and processed by different experts using different methods, resulting in no interoperable data collections.

To overcome these limitations, **Blue-Cloud 2026 project** is developing three **data-intensive Workbenches (WB)** for **physical** (Temperature, Salinity), **eutrophication** (Nutrients, Chlorophyll, Oxygen) and **ecosystem-level** (Plankton biomass, diversity) variables. Leveraging on the **Blue-Cloud collaborative web-based environment**, enhanced discovery and access services and relevant cloud-computing resources, these Workbenches integrate the latest data collections from major **European and global Blue Data Infrastructures** to create consistent, harmonized, **highly-qualified EOV & EBV datasets** through **cloud-based analytical pipelines**.

The resulting EOV & EBV datasets and workflows allows users to rapidly generate **accurate, value-added data products** for ocean monitoring, modeling and simulation scenarios, improving **research** and **decision-making** in areas such as climate change adaptation, sustainable blue economy and marine habitat restoration.

As part of the activities under **WP7 “Exploitation, Strategic Roadmap to 2030 and Sustainability”** and **Task 7.2 “Developing an exploitation plan for Blue-Cloud’s assets”**, the deliverable presents **individual exploitation plans** for each WB, detailing their scope, outputs, target users, asset ownership, exploitation pathways and key exploitation channels, key performance indicators (KPIs), and required resources to ensure the **operational uptake, long-term impact** and **accessibility** of the Workbenches’ results.

This deliverable also aligns with the strategic vision of the **Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030**, and provides the Workbenches first contributions to the project’s **Exploitation and Sustainability plan** (D7.3 and D7.5), thus contributing to the long-term uptake and accessibility of the project’s results to foster advanced and open marine science.

The **key findings** can be summarized as follow:

Accessibility and reusability of the results beyond the project’s end is facilitated through the deployment of the Workbenches in the **Blue-Cloud VRE & catalogue**, which benefits from the **alignment activities** of Blue-Cloud2026 **with European initiatives** such as EOSC, EDITO, EMODnet and CMEMS to reach the

Workbenches primary users (scientists, data modelers) but also intermediary & end-users (policymakers, blue economy stakeholders, citizens).

The Workbenches operational uptake and long-term impact are secured through the **active involvement of Blue Data Infrastructures and European Data Aggregators experts** in the Workbench design, and through the **multiple synergies** and collaborations being developed with other European research projects. Dissemination activities, scientific publications & targeted training will help expand the user base and foster easy adoption in the **research** and **education sectors**.

Finally, the deliverable also emphasizes the **necessity of sustained engagement** of the different stakeholders **beyond the project's conclusion**, to continue tailoring data products requirements to the emerging societal needs, and optimizing data workflows to meet evolving demands, thus achieving a lasting impact.

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1. Objective & scope of the document

The goal of this deliverable is to provide **Individual Exploitation Plans** for each of the three Workbenches of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project, as part of the outcomes of **WP7 “Exploitation, Strategic Roadmap to 2030 and Sustainability”** and **Task 7.2 “Developing an exploitation plan for Blue-Cloud’s assets”**.

Within the **Blue-Cloud 2026 research project**, the **Essential Ocean Variables (EOV) & Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBV)** workbenches partners develop advanced, data-intensive analytical workflows to easily produce harmonized, consistent and highly qualified dataset for selected EOV & EBV, namely physical variables (Temperature, Salinity), eutrophication variables (Nutrients, Chlorophyll, Oxygen) and ecosystem-level variables (Plankton biomass, Plankton diversity), integrating the latest release of major in-situ observation datasets from established **European and global Blue Data Infrastructures (BDI)**. These workflows are a means for **ocean scientists, data managers and modelers** to rapidly obtain up-to-date & consistent **EOV/EBV data products** that will serve as a reliable basis for **ocean validation, assessment, monitoring and simulation** models and applications. Moreover, the workbenches activities require a tight **collaborative approach** with the input BDIs to establish continuous feedback on data access services, data FAIRness, and quality, benefiting the entire information and knowledge value chain.

Recognizing the strategic importance of such results, this deliverable compiles **realistic plans** proposed by the Workbenches’ partners to be deployed during and **beyond the project’s lifespan** to allow the uptake of their results by a wide range of users, and guarantee they remain **accessible and impactful**, supporting long-term advancements in marine research. As such, the document provides valuable insights to shape **Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030, T7.3 Blue-Cloud 2026 Exploitation Plan and Blue-Cloud 2026 Sustainability Strategy & Plan**, in order to help Blue-Cloud2026 reach its desired impact, i.e. the successful evolution of the FAIR marine digital knowledge ecosystem required to support the EU Green Deal and the UN Agenda 2030.

This document is divided in several sections: the first section explains how the Workbenches align with the overarching **Blue-Cloud 2026 strategy** and identify **key channels** prioritized to ensure the exploitation of their results, the second section delivers **individual exploitation plans** for each Workbench, detailing its components (scope & outputs, target users, asset owners, exploitation pathways and exploitation measures) and the **resources** necessary for successful exploitation, the third section defines KPI and targets for the Workbenches and the fourth section highlights additional **exploitation opportunities across Blue-Cloud’s Key Exploitable Results (KER)**.

2. Exploitation strategy for Blue-Cloud 2026 Workbenches

The core objective of Work Package (WP) 3 “**Blue-Cloud Data-Intensive EOV Workbenches**” of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project is to design, manage and run analytical workflows in the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE), demonstrating the added-value that Blue-Cloud brings to the marine knowledge value chain, and its contribution to relevant EU policy objectives. As part of this work, three Workbenches are being developed for the physics, eutrophication and ecosystem EOVs.

The objective of the Blue-Cloud 2026 Workbenches is to develop, validate and document new analytical workflows for regularly producing sets of harmonized and validated data collections for a selection of physical and biogeochemical EOVs. Each of these Workbenches has been defined as a **Key Exploitable Result** of the Blue Cloud 2026 project and is meant to be made available to a variety of users beyond the project Consortium, for use, exploitation and long-term impact. This aligns with the **Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030**, which establishes a long-term vision, a mission, and five strategic paths of action for the evolution of Blue-Cloud, namely:

- **Strategic Action Path 1:** Sustain the flow of FAIR & open marine data into Blue-Cloud.
- **Strategic Action Path 2:** Trigger the development of innovative data analytics methods around priority environmental thematics to inspire and guide the Blue-Cloud community towards further evolving applications in support of key policy objectives.
- **Strategic Action Path 3:** (Further) Federate with key marine data, research and e-infrastructures and strategic initiatives (e.g., EOSC, EDITO-Infra) to enhance value to users.
- **Strategic Action Path 4:** (Further) Grow a thriving ocean open science community, leveraging skills, incentives and rewards and promoting wide dissemination of FAIR methods incubated in Blue-Cloud to boost innovation at a wider scale.
- **Strategic Action Path 5:** Connect and align with wider developments and other communities to contribute to a European and a global, international knowledge system in support of the EU Green Deal and the UN Agenda 2030.

The Workbenches fall within the Strategic Action Path 2, showcasing the value of developing specific, innovative data analytics methods around priority environmental thematics (see section 2.1). A common **exploitation strategy** has been devised for all Workbenches & V Labs, clustering all exploitation measures around three core channels to contribute across the above strategic action paths, namely:

- Exploitation via the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment.
- Exploitation via European and/or international marine data services and/or aggregators.

- Exploitation via the European Digital Twin Ocean.
- Exploitation via the European Open Science Cloud.

2.1. Identification of Key Exploitable Results

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project features two different types of “demonstrators”, namely “Workbenches” and “Virtual Labs”. Specifically, Blue-Cloud 2026 is developing as Key Exploitable Results three Workbenches (KER #1, KER #2, and KER #3, respectively), and five Virtual Labs (KER #4, KER #5, KER #6, KER #7, and KER #8, respectively). As the focus of this document is on the Blue-Cloud Workbenches, the following are covered in this document:

- EOVS Workbench for Physics – Temperature & Salinity - KER #1
- EOVS Workbench for Eutrophication – Chlorophyll, Nutrients, Oxygen - KER #2
- EOVS & EBV Workbench for Ecosystems - KER #3

2.2. Exploitation channels prioritised

As earlier introduced, when defining exploitation objectives and measures for Blue-Cloud 2026 KERs, three specific channels have been prioritized towards long-term impact, as part of a common exploitation strategy:

- **Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment:** The Blue-Cloud VRE is the primary exploitation channel for any of the Blue-Cloud Workbenches and the data products and/or applications they offer. The Workbenches offer (open, reproducible and collaborative) resources of interest to the marine research & innovation community, which can be leveraged to further develop added-value applications for other (secondary or tertiary) users. Sustaining the exploitation of available Workbenches supports the objective of growing a thriving community of open science practitioners in the marine domain, which is one of the overarching objectives of the Blue-Cloud ecosystem of services. A rich and diverse portfolio of Workbenches V Labs further contributes to enhance the attractiveness of the Blue-Cloud platform, and will be considered as a pivotal element of its exploitation strategy and plan (D7.3 – Joint Exploitation Plan), which will be shaped and delivered by December 2025.
- **European and/or international marine data services and/or aggregators:** Identified in Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030 as “intermediate, secondary users”, European marine data services such as EMODnet or Copernicus Marine Service offer a win-win, publishing channel for Blue-Cloud’s V Labs resulting data products. As part of its value proposition, Blue-Cloud seeks to enhance the interoperability of marine data to accelerate the transformation of marine data to products, in

support of marine knowledge. Ingesting Blue-Cloud's data products into European, long-term marine data services and aggregators would ensure wide dissemination to a much broader user base (SMEs, industry, policy makers, NGOs, etc.) than currently Blue-Cloud's, ensuring they can be re-used by researchers and innovators to deliver to the needs of decision makers in support of wider economic, societal and policy developments. In addition, these data aggregators will benefit from the ability to integrate Blue-Cloud's Workbenches into the data validation process. The same logic applies to leveraging other data aggregators and/or services, whether European or international, as relevant, for broader dissemination.

- **The European Digital Twin Ocean:** The European Digital Twin Ocean (DTO) is a high-resolution, multi-dimensional, and near real-time digital representation of the ocean. Designed to be accessible to citizens, scientists, entrepreneurs, and policymakers, it will provide innovative tools to transform the way we understand, manage and interact with the ocean. Blue-Cloud is positioning its innovation ecosystem as a contributor to the EU DTO, acting as an incubator of innovative methods and/or applications. By leveraging the alignment efforts of Blue-Cloud2026 and EDITO -the public infrastructure of the EU DTO-, orchestrated through the DTO Task Force, the integration of the Workbenches outputs into the [EDITO](#) platform will enhance their interoperability and outreach, enabling these resources to be combined with global ocean observation data, advanced modeling and AI tools on high-performance computing platforms to support dynamic ocean simulations scenarios and decision-making tools. Alignment of EDITO with similar global initiatives (DITTO, DestinationEarth) will extend the outreach and allow transdisciplinary uses.
- **The European Open Science Cloud:** EOSC is growing and consolidating as the European data space for the academic, scientific and research community in Europe. Since its inception, Blue-Cloud has been conceived as the thematic "marine" component of EOSC, setting up and offering services seeking to bridge and connect the marine community with relevant EOSC developments i.e., the EOSC EU Node, the platform officially launched in October 2024 to support multi-disciplinary and multi-national research promoting the use of FAIR data and supplementary services in Europe and beyond. The emerging development of the EOSC EU Node and complementary thematic nodes opens new opportunities to further anchor Blue-Cloud's position as a marine thematic open science node servicing the EOSC community. With this in mind, all Workbenches will consider and seek to leverage exploitation opportunities via EOSC, tailoring measures to their respective landscape, as relevant (e.g., seeking synergies with other ongoing EOSC projects, disciplines, etc).

The specific exploitation measures devised for these channels are further described in the Individual Exploitation Plan of each Workbench, respectively, as described in sections 3-5 of this document.

3. KER#1 : Blue-Cloud EOV Workbench for Physics

3.1. Description and characterisation of the KER

The EOV Workbench for Physics will develop an analytical workflow to produce added value Temperature and Salinity datasets integrating data coming from multiple “Blue” (marine and related) Data Infrastructures (BDIs). The expected output is twofold: 1) the workflow embedded in the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment and, 2) the dataset.

The realization of the EOV Workbench for Physics is meant to speed up the marine data value chain and rapidly derive midstream data products and downstream information products (i.e. Ocean Heat Content indicator in Marine Environmental Indicators ((MEI) Vlab 4). In the present landscape, a digital ecosystem of blue data infrastructures assembles, harmonizes and validates marine data coming from different data providers and different platforms, but none of the present infrastructures has a complete database. The data integration from multiple infrastructures has the aim of maximizing spatial and temporal data coverage, increasing the quality of the derived products (i.e. climatologies, reanalysis, monitoring indicators). Previous ad-hoc solutions exist to create integrated EOVs datasets. For example, a prior analysis conducted within the framework of EU SeaDataCloud project, finalized to the generation of regional climatologies for the EU sea basins, showed the gain integrating data from SeaDataNet infrastructure with CORA (Coriolis Ocean Dataset for Reanalysis) product distributed by the Copernicus Marine Service and/or data from the World Ocean Database distributed by NOAA. The integration process was based on the simplifying assumption that in case of duplicates the SeaDataNet version was retained. The aim was not to release the integrated datasets thus there was no need to harmonize the metadata. This integration (data from SeaDataNet and CMEMS) has been done also by Escudier et al. (2022) for the data to be assimilated in the CMEMS Mediterranean Sea reanalysis. The resulting Workbench data pipeline will be able to run at any time, giving the user the possibility to handle duplicates and to perform additional validation on the data, according to the data use. Data integration will always consider the latest data versions available from the source BDIs, relying on the BEACON (<https://beacon.maris.nl/>) synchronization procedure. The Blue-Cloud datasets will undergo further QC procedures to guarantee integrity, consistency of the Blue-Cloud added value dataset.

KER outputs:

- **KER#1.1:** EOV Physic Workbench’s pipeline: script & workflow

- **KER#1.2:** Highly qualified Temperature & Salinity EOVS dataset (Mediterranean Sea and global ocean)

3.2. Asset owner(s)

The asset owners are **Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia (INGV)**, **Hellenic Center for Marine Research (HCMR)**, **Institut français de recherche pour l'exploitation de la mer (Ifremer)**, **OceanScope** and **POKaPOK**.

- **MARIS** and **BODC** provide the integrated data & harmonising services (using BEACON and the semantic mapping obtained with the Semantic Analyser) that produce the integrated and harmonised input dataset for the Workbench.
- **AWI** provides the webODV service on the VRE for data exploration, analysis and visualization. webODV can also be used for duplicate detection and removal, and further quality control analysis of the integrated dataset, if the domain of investigation is not too wide.
- **Pokapok** provides CloneWars software for duplicate detection and real time MinMax software for quality control.
- **OceanScope** provides the delay mode MinMax software version.
- **INGV** provides the notebooks for the Mediterranean climatology computation.
- **MARIS, Ifremer, INGV, HCMR, Oceanscope** provide the beacon queries for input data access.

3.3. Target users

Primary users:

- **Researchers:** Modelers, marine data scientists, and the climate change community could use the Workbench's pipeline to generate their integrated dataset selecting the input BDIs sources, the target region, the analysis time period, the further QC to be applied according to their needs, and validate their results.
- **Students:** The Workbench's pipeline could also be used to train new scientists on open science data and tools.

Intermediary users:

- **Data aggregators:** EMODnet, CMEMS, SeaDataNet could add the highly qualified EOVS dataset to their catalogs and exploit the WB workflow to improve their products.

- European DTO: EOV datasets and Workbenches operational pipelines can be integrated and deployed in the EDITO platform for discovery and reusability by users seeking to build Digital Twins applications.
- IOC/IODE Ocean Best Practices System: ingestion of pipeline standards as a new method in the Ocean Best Practice System (OBPS).

End users:

- Reporting activities: CMEMS Ocean State Report, BAMS State of Climate, IPCC could exploit the Blue-Cloud datasets to obtain always up to date monitoring indicators.

3.4. Exploitation pathways and milestones

In order to ensure the uptake of the workbench's results by their primary users (**researchers, data scientists, ocean modelers**), the EOV datasets (KER#1.2), pipeline's components (KER#1.1) and associated documentation will be deployed on the Blue-Cloud's infrastructure and made available freely to all users of the **Blue-Cloud VRE** during the project. The Blue-Cloud VRE offers the cloud environment and the computing resources necessary for any user to run the pipeline and perform their own processes to obtain a qualified dataset on the selected variables of their choice. The Blue-Cloud VRE will be maintained for 2 years after the end of the project, and aims at being offered as a service to all ocean scientists on a long-term basis as part of an **EU EOSC marine thematic Node**, enhancing reuse of the Workbench's result by scientists and researchers from diverse backgrounds.

Online repositories, offering free, open, secure and sustained access to the Workbench results, will be used as dissemination channels: **Zenodo** for the documentation, **Seano**, **Blue-Cloud Catalogue** and **EOSC EU Node Catalogue** for the EOV dataset, **Github** for the script and the lesson learned will be submitted to the **Ocean Best Practices System**. Publication of the EOV Workbench method as new method in the OBPS repository is a key action to reach a high impact among ocean scientists, as the UNESCO Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) OBPS aims to foster the standardization and adoption of relevant best practices across ocean communities globally. Dissemination events such as **Blue-Cloud 2026 webinar**, **Blue-Cloud 2026 Hackathon** and **Blue-Cloud 2026 Training Academy** will promote the results to various stakeholders, such as **ocean data managers, scientists** but also **students**, and help with their early adoption in **research and education sectors**. Data papers and scientific articles will be published in peer-reviewed journals such as the **Journal of Data Science and Analytics** to further disseminate the results in the scientific sphere and trigger new research.

The highly qualified Temperature & Salinity EOV datasets produced during the project will also be proposed for integration into the catalogs of different **European Data aggregators** such as **CMEMS**,

SeaDataNet and EMODnet Physics under a CC-BY license, building on the involvement of representative organisations in the Blue-Cloud 2026 project and as Workbench’s participants. By making use of the dissemination activities of such infrastructures, the Workbench data products will reach a wide audience, and will maximize their exploitation through the associated services offered by such European initiatives.

The Workbench KER will be integrated in the **European DTO**: the EOV datasets (KER#1.2) produced during Blue-Cloud 2026 will enrich the core DTO by being ported in the **EDITO datalake**, and will therefore be offered as consistent, highly qualified and reliable data product for temperature and salinity EOV to serve as basis to climatologies, models, indicators maps, monitoring content and decision-making applications. In addition, the Workbench’s pipeline (KER#1.2), with all its components, is planned to be offered, in its operational version, as analytical service through the **EDITO platform**, thanks to the **synergies** being developed in the Blue-Cloud 2026 project with EDITO-Infra to connect both infrastructures and continuous alignment between EDITO and Blue-Cloud 2026, established through the project’s DTO Task Force, which benefits from **MOI’s and VLIZ’s partnership**. This will allow users to produce easily and regularly updated EOV datasets with consistent QC. It is a key pathway to a wide impact of the Workbench’s results, extending its application to ocean data modelers, climate change community but also policy-makers, citizens and entrepreneurs.

The uptake of the results in the **operational activities** of the Workbench partners and the exploration of their **integration in national initiatives** is also envisioned, to maximize the exploitation of the Workbench outputs.

Finally, **reporting activities**, such as international partnerships and candidature as authors of the Copernicus Ocean State Report and others assessment reports, could further increase the physics Workbench impact.

3.5. Exploitation measures committed and planned

The exploitation measures committed & planned (subject to availability of resources) by Consortium partners are outlined in Table 1.

Exploitation measures	Related KER	When	Who	Where/How
Publication of scripts/pipeline notebook	2.1	Summer 2025	INGV and WB partners	Online (Blue-Cloud VRE)
Blue-Cloud Hackathon	2.1	Fall 2025	all WB partners	Online

Exploitation measures	Related KER	When	Who	Where/How
Blue-Cloud webinar	2.1, 2.2	Summer 2026	INGV and WB partners	Online
Publication of scripts/pipeline notebook in Github	2.1	Summer 2026	INGV and WB partners	Online (Github)
Publication of EOv datasets in the project’s catalogue	2.2	2026	INGV and WB partners	Blue-Cloud Catalogue
Publication of EOv datasets in European Data aggregators	2.2 2.3	Summer 2026	INGV and WB partners	EMODnet Physics and EOSC catalogues
Integration of WB outputs in EDITO platform	2.1, 2.2	Summer 2026	WB partners with WP5 support	EDITO Infra (synergy with EDITO, inputs from T2.4/DTO Task Force)
Publication of derived gridded-field climatology	2.3	Planned (2026)	INGV	Online repository (Seanoë)
Pipeline method proposed as new method to OBPS	2.1	Planned (2026)	WB partners	OBPS repository
Potential provision of helpdesk support service	2.1	Planned (2027-2030)	WB partners	
Potential publication of updated highly qualified EOv datasets	2.2	Planned (2027-2030)	WB partners	
Potential Training support to users	2.1, 2.3	Planned (2027-2030)	WB partners	
Potential publication of updated scripts	2.1	Planned (2027-2030)	WB partners	Github

Table 1 - Exploitation measures committed and planned for Workbench « Physics »

3.6. Resources needed to implement the Exploitation Plan

The WB 1 pipeline will demonstrate the feasibility of data integration from different sources adding value to the present available EOvs datasets, but since the datascape and the technological advancements are rapidly evolving, only a continuous maintenance and update of the operational chain would guarantee its results.

The systematic update and release of EOV datasets would require:

- Human and financial resources;
- A framework for data managers and scientists to continuously develop semantic harmonization, data exploration/analysis and visualization service (webODV), duplicate analysis and further QC tools;
- An IT infrastructure to run the pipeline;
- The data providers (source BDI) expertise to update beacon instances and queries according to the evolving data model;
- The implementation of a user interface to easily run the pipeline.

The provision of a help desk support would ensure maintenance & viable use of the Workbench's pipeline in time is also highly dependent on additional human and financial resources.

4. KER#2 : Blue-Cloud EOV Workbench for Eutrophication

4.1. Description and characterisation of the KER

Currently, data collections for selected EOV are based on small data packages that are processed by different experts (e.g. WOD, EMODnet, CMEMS) using different methods and are computationally intensive, resulting in no interoperable data collections.

The Eutrophication Workbench addresses three specific problems:

- 1) Mapping of essential metadata;
- 2) Common quality control procedures;
- 3) Identification and treatment of duplicates, using Blue-Cloud datalake development and specialized cloud-based software tools.

These will enable efficient dataset aggregation and harmonization to produce validated EOV data collections, in this case for nutrients, chlorophyll and oxygen, by combining the efforts of two major groups of data experts in Europe (EMODnet and CMEMS). A specific protocol is being jointly established to identify and address potential duplicate observations.

Currently, multiple datasets in different data infrastructures use their own QC/QA and need to be synchronized manually. Leveraging Blue-Cloud's cloud storage and computing services, and its Virtual Research Environment, offering a new analytical framework, the Workbench will enable the integration,

validation, and analysis of large amounts of data using common methods. High quality datasets for a selection of EOVs for eutrophication variables will be created and made publicly available.

KER Outputs:

- **KER#2.1:** EOV Eutrophication Workbench's pipeline to be used for data integration and validation: script & workflow;
- **KER#2.2:** Highly qualified EOV datasets on Chlorophyll, Nutrients and Oxygen (North-East Atlantic Sea and Global Ocean), in NetCDF and ODV format;
- **KER#2.3:** Derived gridded-fields using DIVAnd to produce climatology maps for the North East Atlantic and European seas.

4.2. Asset owner(s)

The asset owners are **Istituto nazionale di oceanografia e di geofisica sperimentale (OGS)**, **Institut français de recherche pour l'exploitation de la mer (Ifremer)**, **Hellenic Center for Marine Research (HCMR)** and **POKaPOK**.

MARIS and **BODC** provide the data query & harmonizing services (using BEACON and the semantic mapping obtained using the Semantic Analyzer and the Eutrophication WB Literature Survey) that produce the harmonized & validated dataset for the Workbench.

AWI provides a customized webODV service on the VRE for data exploration, analysis and visualization. webODV can also be used for duplicate detection and removal, and further quality control analysis of the integrated datasets.

POKaPOK provides a web application for duplicate detection and a tool for additional methods for quality control.

OGS and **HCMR** provide the scripts to run the DIVAnd climatology computations and gridded maps.

MARIS, **Ifremer**, **HCMR**, **OGS** and **Pokapok** provide the beacon queries for input data access.

4.3. Target users

Primary users:

- Researchers:
 - Biogeochemical modelers can use the merged datasets for more accurate initial and boundary conditions.

- Data managers can perform duplicate checks and QC and obtain more robust statistical ranges of eutrophication parameters for quality control and assurance.
- Data managers can improve the process of data integration and validation by working in a shared environment in a collaborative way.
- It can also benefit research institutes and universities, who can integrate these datasets in their operational activities and derive services or train students and young researchers.
- Partners in Blue-Cloud and sister EU projects.

Intermediary users:

- Data catalogues: EMODnet Chemistry data products, CMEMS In Situ Service can integrate the results of the Workbench into their operational activities and catalogue and derive services.
- European DTO: The Workbenches can be offered to EDITO users (marine data scientists, modelers, researchers, and software developers), if deployed on the EDITO platform.

End users:

- Policy makers/EU initiatives: Resulting EOVS datasets are a valuable asset for EU MSFD Technical Groups, Regional Seas Conventions, EEA & EU directives.
- Global initiatives: Likewise, for UN Ocean Decade Actions, UN Global Oxygen Database, UN SDG 14.3.1 Ocean Acidification Federated System, UN SDG Indicators.

4.4. Exploitation pathways and milestones

To ensure the widespread adoption of the workbench's results by **researchers, biogeochemical modelers and ocean scientists**, the workbench's pipeline (KER#2.1), resulting highly qualified EOVS datasets (chlorophyll, oxygen and nutrients) (KER#2.2), climatologies (KER#2.3) and related documentation will be deployed on the **Blue-Cloud infrastructure** during the project and made available freely to all the **Blue-Cloud VRE** users' upon registration during the project. The Blue-Cloud VRE offers the cloud environment and the computing resources necessary for any user to run the pipeline and perform their own processes in a collaborative and shared way, to obtain a qualified dataset on the selected variables of their choice. The Blue-Cloud VRE is built upon CNR-ISTI and D4Science infrastructure, engaged in maintaining the VRE for 2 years after the end of the project. Furthermore, the Blue-Cloud VRE is planned to be offered as a long-term service to ocean scientists and interested users as part of an **EOSC EU marine thematic Node**, thus ensuring availability and reuse of the Workbench results **beyond the end of the project** by researchers from various disciplines and a wide range of users.

In addition, the workbench's EOV datasets (KER#2.2) and derived climatologies for regional seas (KER#2.3) will be published **by the end of the project** in standardised netCDF format under **CC-BY license** in **open data repository (Seanoë, Blue-Cloud 2026 & EOSC EU Node)**, and integrated in **EMODnet Chemistry** and **Copernicus Marine service**, leveraging on the established services and large user bases of these major **European data aggregators** to further enhance the uptake of the highly qualified EOV outputs. A key outcome will be a highest accuracy in the data products & indicators produced for **EU directives** (MSFD, Habitat directive, etc.) and reported to **regional sea conventions**, supporting policy decisions related to eutrophication management. Blue Cloud 2026 project partners (**POKAPOK, OGS**) who are heavily involved in the management of blue data infrastructures (EMODnet, CMEMS) will address the respective communities. Integration of the EOV data products in other global data repositories, such as **UN Global Oxygen Database**, is also planned by the end of the project.

The Workbench partners will engage in several events and tools **during the project** to further disseminate the Workbench's results and raise awareness of eutrophication, acidification and ocean health to scientific but also public audience via **Blue-Cloud 2026 webinars**, participation in relevant **conferences**, and digital communication (**website, social media**). The EOV data products (KER#2.2) and the pipeline (KER#2.1), once finalized, will be the object of publication as **scientific articles** and **data papers** in **peer-review scientific journals**, highlighting the new methodologies for dataset harmonization and quality control that can be utilized by **scientists** and **modelers** for further research. Publication of the Workbench's method (with QC procedures and semantic rules) in the **UNESCO IOC OBPS** will help position this methodology as a **best practice** and state-of-the-art tool for oceanographic and environmental research, and foster its adoption by the **scientific community**. The publication of **training support** through the **Blue-Cloud Training Academy** will provide guidance to **students, early career scientists** and other parties interested in the Workbench's results. Furthermore, making first results available to the **Blue-Cloud hackathon** users (2025) and to sister European **Infra-EOSC projects** partners such as **FAIR-EASE** will facilitate early adoption by a diverse audience **before the end of the project**.

The workbench's key outputs will also be integrated into EDITO, the public infrastructure of the **European Digital Twin of the Ocean**. **By the end of the project**, the EOV datasets (KER#2.2) and derived climatologies (KER#2.3) will be made available in analysis-ready interoperable formats via EMODnet into the **EDITO Datalake**, and the workbench's pipeline (KER#2.1) and components will aim to be deployed on the **EDITO platform** as new process and data processing, visualization and analytical tools, leveraging on Blue-Cloud 2026 and EDITO continuous alignment through the **DTO Task Force**. Through integration on EDITO, the highly qualified, consistent and harmonized EOV datasets and climatologies, can be a reliable contribution to the development of **eutrophication indicators**, maps, monitoring applications and **large-scale models** for ocean health and eutrophication impact assessment, supporting **decision-making**

processes and feeding climate change and **ocean previsions and simulation scenarios**. They may also find uses in **industry applications** such as aquaculture, fisheries and coastal management. The Workbench’s pipeline will empower Blue Data Infrastructures and research organizations scientists and data managers with a simple, automatic process to perform duplicate checks and quality control on the latest version of the relevant data sources, for their time, period and parameters of interest. By being ported in the core infrastructure of the European DTO, it will benefit from EDITO’s cloud infrastructure and environment to be run seamlessly and connected with diverse applications, even **beyond the end of the project**.

The uptake of the results in the **operational activities** of the Workbench partners and the exploration of their **integration in national initiatives** is also envisioned, as part of the exploitation of the Workbench outcomes.

4.5. Exploitation measures committed and planned

The exploitation measures committed & planned (subject to availability of resources) by Consortium partners are outlined in Table 2.

Exploitation measures	Related KER	When	Who	Where/How
Blue-Cloud 2026 Hackathon	2.1	Fall 2025	WB partners	Online
Publication of scripts/pipeline notebook in Blue-Cloud VRE	2.1	Fall 2025	WB partners	Online (Blue-Cloud VRE)
Blue-Cloud 2026 Webinar	2.1, 2.2	Summer 2026	WB partners	Online
Publication of EOv datasets	2.2	2026	WB partners	Blue-Cloud Catalogue, EOsc EU Node and Catalogues, Seanoe
Publication of scripts/pipeline notebook in Github	2.1	Summer 2026	WB partners	Online (Github)
Publication of derived gridded-field climatologies	2.3	2026	WB partners	Blue-Cloud Catalogue, Zenodo
Ingestion of EOv highly qualified data products in European Data Aggregators infrastructure	2.2	Summer 2026	WB partners	EMODnet catalogue, CMEMS in-situ service

Exploitation measures	Related KER	When	Who	Where/How
Integration of WB pipeline in EDITO platform	2.1	Summer 2026	WB partners, WP5, T2.4	EDITO Infra (synergy with EDITO, inputs from T2.4/DTO Task Force)
Ingestion of EOv data products in UN Global Oxygen Database	2.1	2026	WB partners	UN Global Oxygen Database
Integration of WB pipeline as a workflow in Galaxy	2.1	Planned (2026)	WB partners, WP5	Galaxy (synergy with FAIR-EASE)
Pipeline method proposed as new method to OBPS	2.1	Planned (2026)	WB partners	OBPS repository
Potential provision of helpdesk support service	2.1	Planned (2027-2030)	WB partners	Blue cloud ticketing. "Request support" button on the VRE dashboard
Potential publication of updated highly qualified EOv datasets	2.2	Planned (2027-2030)	WB partners	Blue cloud Catalogue
Potential training support to users	2.1, 2.3	Planned (2027-2030)	WB partners	handbooks and Jupyter notebooks
Potential publication of updated scripts in Github	2.1	Planned (2027-2030)	WB partners	Github

Table 2 - Exploitation measures committed and planned for Workbench « Eutrophication »

4.6. Resources needed to implement the Exploitation Plan

In general, the Workbench is highly dependent on human and financial resources as well as IT infrastructure.

Provision of a help desk support to ensure maintenance and good use of the WB pipeline and publication of updated EOv datasets demands specific resources and framework for data managers and scientists to perform new duplicate check & QC, the implementation of a user-friendly interface and the IT infrastructure to run the pipeline, data provider expertise to update beacon queries according to new data model if updated.

5. KER#3 : Blue-Cloud EOV Workbench for Ecosystem

5.1. Description and characterisation of the KER

The primary purpose of the Ecosystem Workbench is to improve the availability, quality, and interoperability of large collections of plankton distribution, biomass and biodiversity observations and extrapolated biogeographies. A habitat modelling workflow will generate high-quality interpolated maps of these plankton entities at the global scale, in order to produce ecosystem-level EOVs.

In recent years, collections of plankton observations have been increasingly growing in number and availability across taxa and data types (e.g. nets; imaging; omics). These quantitative datasets are not standardized across data types, nor associated with a common framework to extrapolate their distribution in space and time. To fill this gap, the Ecosystem-Workbench provides a unique and standardized framework to produce extrapolated maps from all available data sources, with comparable and explicit outputs and quality checks, based on up-to-date, community-accepted best modelling practices.

The Ecosystem-Workbench will be directly exploited by Consortium Partners (see section 5.2) as a standard for habitat modelling, producing diversity and biomass products across different data types and taxa or functional levels. Such products will provide EOVs and EBVs updated on a regular basis, for interest to researchers and decision makers. We will also provide extrapolated maps and modelling pipelines to a range of sister EU projects (H2020 project AtlantECO, HORIZON project BiOcean5D) and provide assistance and mapping services for researchers from international partner institutions (members of the AtlantECO and BiOcean5D consortium, European marine species distribution modeling community as reached through ETH's and NOC's recent species distribution modelling workshop (September 2023)). The pipeline is versatile, covering three data types (binary, continuous and relative abundances) and three major plankton sampling methodologies (metagenomics, imaging and traditional observations) and can easily be applied to a range of biotic and non-biotic geo-referenced ocean variables and is thus of interest for use in other fields of biological oceanography, marine biogeochemistry and related fields beyond the end of BlueCloud2026. Resulting maps are further being delivered to stakeholders from the environmental policy, conservation and management sector.

In addition to a common framework and standard for marine habitat modelling, this workbench will provide a dynamic data access to plankton collections across all major data types currently used to quantify the marine microbiome and global plankton communities, as well as environmental predictors through the BlueCloud2026 and D4 Science infrastructure. Thus, we offer a standardized, dynamic, user-friendly, cloud computing framework, allowing to explore plankton biogeography and diversity within and across these various data collections, and provide a thorough quality evaluation of our products.

Workbench's outputs:

- **KER#3.1:** Workbench pipeline "CEPHALOPOD" (Docker container with R code)
- **KER#3.2:** Highly qualified EOVS datasets (global plankton diversity, distribution and trait biogeography)
- **KER#3.3:** Training material for tutorials and/or labs
- **KER#3.4:** Scientific papers in peer-reviewed journals
- **KER#3.5:** Joint collaborations

5.2. Asset owner(s)

The asset owners are **ETH Zurich (ETHZ)**, **Sorbonne University (SU)** and the **European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL)**.

5.3. Target users

The habitat modelling framework aims to target a wide audience, providing a user-friendly interface with default settings for non-expert users, as well as a transparent and flexible pipeline settings for expert users. The framework will further provide standard quality-controlled output products on global plankton biodiversity and biomass. The target audience includes:

Primary users:

- Researchers: marine ecosystem modelling community (from ecological modelers to Earth system modelers)
- Partners in Blue-Cloud and sister EU projects (AtlantECO, BioOcean5D)

Intermediary users:

- Education sector: workshops, teaching at school, BSc, MSc and PhD level, summer schools
- Data catalogues and data aggregators: EMODnet data products
- European DTO: EDITO platform users

End users:

- Policy makers (national, European, global): map-based decision-making to serve policymakers' needs that can then adjust policies in accordance with this new knowledge, joint IUCN policy
- Ecosystem managers and environmental conservationists
- Museum curators: Biogeographic maps of species distribution for marine plankton species
- Artists: Maps of plankton diversity and biomass

5.4. Exploitation pathways and milestones

To ensure a large uptake of the Workbench KER by **researchers** and the **marine ecosystem modelling community**, free, open access to all resources available in the Workbench, respectively KER#3.1, KER#3.2 and KER#3.3, will be granted to all users under a **CC-by license** during and after the project. The R code associated with the pipeline (KER#3.1) will also be available via **GitHub** repository, alongside the related documentation, and containerized using Docker, to facilitate reuse and portability to other infrastructures. These results will be deployed in the **Blue-Cloud VRE**, offering the possibility to users to use the products and the CEPHALOPOD pipeline regardless of their expertise and local IT resources. Following the project's completion, the Blue-Cloud VRE will be maintained for an additional two years and is envisioned to become a long-term service for the ocean science community. It aims to be integrated into the EOSC ecosystem, possibly as an **EU EOSC marine thematic Node**, ensuring the long-term reuse of the workbench's outputs by scientists and researchers across disciplines. In any case, the Workbench's results will be ported in the **EOSC EU Node Catalogues** at the end of the project, and the associated documentation published in **Zenodo** online repository.

The Workbench EOVS data products and analytical pipeline will aim for integration in EDITO, the public infrastructure of the **European DTO the end of the project**, leveraging on the synergies developed between Blue-Cloud 2026 and EDITO-Infra and EDITO-Model projects in the framework of the Blue-Cloud 2026 **DTO Task Force** that aims at aligning Blue-Cloud's 2026 with European DTO developments. This action is key to maximize outcomes of the Workbench beyond the project, since it will allow users to obtain up-to-date, consistent, qualified and interoperable plankton diversity, biomass and biogeography datasets, enhancing the accuracy of derived models informing **conservation** strategies, ecosystem-based management, sustainable **fishery** management, map-based decision tools and feed climate simulation scenarios.

Once peer-reviewed, the ingestion of extrapolated maps of biodiversity in **EMODnet Biology**, a European data aggregator with a large outreach involving **researchers, modelers and policy-makers (Regional Sea Convention, EEA & EU directives)**, will maximize dissemination and exploitation of these results.

Furthermore, the publication of a **joint policy brief with the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) on marine plankton diversity** planned for the time period after the end of the project will increase awareness among **policymakers**, stakeholders and **citizens** and may pave the way for more sustainable practices and meaningful **conservation** actions.

From the start, the Workbench was built on strong **collaboration** with other European research projects, to ensure fit-for-use results tailored to the needs of different communities of practice. Strong synergies are being built with **AtlantECO** and **BiOcean5D projects**, in the form of **data** (underlying biological data

from microscopy, predictor datasets) and **model outputs exchanges** (e.g. contribution to AtlantECO deliverable AtlantECO-MAPS), as well as **codes** (e.g. mutual fertilization between Blue-Cloud's CEPHALOPOD and AtlantECO's EMOcean Apps) and **joint publications** (e.g. AtlantECO deliverable D2.7), and several **collaborations** with AtlantECO data generators, (Universidade Federal de Sao Carlos, EBI), theoretical ecologists (University of Parma), species distribution modelers (University of Rome) and BiOcean5D species distribution modelers. In addition, the organisation of **training sessions, summer schools and joint workshops** is helping maximize the early adoption of the workbench's results and novel methodology, and create a pool of scientific data users **before the end of the project**.

Collaborations with the **BlueBioTech** community, through synergies with the **BlueRemediomics** project that provides data outputs from MGnify to the Ecosystem Workbench. Exchange of MAG catalogues and data products and the joint analysis of data products are also part of the synergy until the projects end (November 2026).

To reach a broader audience, the results of the Workbench will be disseminated through different events and channels: **Blue-Cloud 2026 webinar, training academy, web news** and **public outreach activities**. A **scientific article** actually under review, scheduled for publication in a peer-reviewed scientific journal in spring 2025, will foster the uptake by **researchers**. The **Blue-Cloud 2026 hackathon**, organised in fall 2025, will help expand the Workbench's user base and encourage broader adoption.

Education sector will be addressed **during and beyond the end of the project** through dedicated **training sessions** with MSc students at ETH (currently ongoing training: 2 ETH MSc students (November, 2024)) and through **ETH yearly university classes** that will make use of maps on plankton biodiversity and biogeography provided by the Workbench in multiple courses such as, e.g., MSc course Global Biogeochemical Cycles and Climate (yearly; spring semester), or the Certificate of Advanced Studies (CAS) in Climate Innovation (yearly: spring semester). Furthermore, ETH has and will contribute **practicals and lectures** on plankton distribution and diversity and the use of species distribution modelling pipeline CEPHALOPOD to the **joint AtlantECO and BiOcean5D Synergy Summer School** (June 2024 and 2025). This will contribute to developing skills and knowledge among the students and early-career researchers and help establish the Workbench as a standard tool in habitat modelling and marine ecosystem research. The publication of a plankton diversity card game as **training material** (KER#3.3) dedicated to Swiss Polar Institute class, a free educational programme reaching 350 school classes across Switzerland with a total of 7000 children (years 5-8), will help raise awareness of plankton diversity impacts in polar regions among **students and citizens**.

For now, no official support is envisaged by IP owners to exploit the Workbench after the project ends. However, the pipeline (KER#3.1) will be used in multiple ongoing science projects that go beyond the end of the project, so the pipeline will be **integrated into core research activities at ETH and SU** and in multiple

partner laboratories as part of multiple EU projects. Exchange between existing and new users will be highly encouraged and facilitated as in-kind contributions. Publications, readme files, Github folders etc. will be published in **FAIR data repositories** for reference and further development.

5.5. Exploitation measures committed and planned

The exploitation measures committed and planned (subject to available resources) by Consortium partners are outlined in Table 3.

Exploitation measures	Related KER	When	Who	Where/How
Summer schools (AtlantECO, BiOceans5D)	3.1, 3.3	June 2024	ETH	Onsite (Ischia, Italy and Zurich, Switzerland). Presentation of CEPHALOPOD results during SynSS (AtlantECO, BiOcean5D, BlueCloud2026) Presentation of the BlueCloud2026 project and WB3 during ETH’s summer school on Research data management
Publication of code on Github	3.1, 3.2	Sept. 2024	ETH	https://github.com/alexschicke/CEPHALOPOD
Upload of WB documentation to Zenodo	3.1, 3.2	Sept. 2024	TRUST-IT	Online (D3.1 : https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13889325)
Training sessions	3.1, 3.3	Oct 2024	ETH	On site. Current training: 2 MSc students and 1 postdoc (SU) in person at ETH
Publication of Plankton diversity card game	3.3	fall/winter 2024/25	ETH	Plankton card games under development (deadline: January, 2025)
Blue-Cloud 2026 Hackathon	3.1, 3.2	April-Oct 2025	ETHZ, SU, EMBL	Online
Peer-reviewed scientific publications and/or data papers	3.4	Spring 2025	ETH, SU	Online

Exploitation measures	Related KER	When	Who	Where/How
University courses at ETH Zurich	3.1, 3.3	Yearly (spring semester)	ETH	Onsite
Synergies with EU H2020 project AtlantECO	3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4	Ongoing, sept. 2025	ETH - EBI	Online/General Assemblies/workshops/exchange of scientists Development of pipeline in collaboration with AtlantECO partners (e.g., University of Rome); training of project members in the use of CEPHALOPOD
Planned cross-fertilisation activities with other VLabs or Workbenches	3.1, 3.2	ongoing (monthly), summer 2026	ETH OGS	Regular WP3 online meetings, SSC meetings; WP3 meetings during GAs and TSCs
Synergies with EU HORIZON project BioOcean5D	3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4	Ongoing, nov. 2026	ETH - EBI	Online/General Assemblies/exchange of researchers data transfer of underlying biological data from microscopy completed; data transfer of jointly produced predictor data sets ongoing (11-24)
Synergies with BlueBiotech, e.g., BlueRemediomics	3.2	Ongoing Nov-2026	EMBL-EBI	Onsite
Ingestion of data products into EMODnet Catalogue	3.2	Planned (2026)	EBI	Online Ingestion of extrapolated maps of biodiversity by EBI partners
Joint Policy Brief w/IUCN		To be defined	ETH	Online
Potential publication of updated scripts in GitHub	3.1	Planned (2027-2030)	ETH	GitHub
Potential publication of updated EOv and EBv datasets	3.2	Planned (2027-2030)	ETH	Online repository

Exploitation measures	Related KER	When	Who	Where/How
Potential additional peer-reviewed scientific publications and/or data papers	3.4	Planned (2027-2030)	ETH, SU	Online
Potential training session for WB users	3.1, 3.4	Planned (2027-2030)	ETH	In person for collaborative work in BiOcean5D and other new national and international projects

Table 3 - Exploitation measures committed & planned for Workbench « Ecosystem »

5.6. Resources needed to implement the Exploitation Plan

Resources needed for the asset owners to offer a help desk service beyond the end of the project:

- 3 PMs / year (researcher)
- 1 PM/ year (technician, scientific programmer)

Potential ORD grants at ETH could be applied for, to maintain helpdesk-type activities, but funding is not guaranteed at this point.

In order to further develop the pipeline, the following resources would be needed:

- 12 PMs (researcher) for further development and incorporation of machine learning methods
- 6 PM (technician, scientific programmer) for scientific visualization and data integration

6. Key Performance Indicators and Targets (2026-2030)

6.1. Common KPI and Targets (2026-2030)

To measure the impact of the exploitation activities planned by the Workbenches, the following KPIs will be considered:

- Number of **users**, **access** and **views** of the Workbenches on the **Blue-Cloud VRE**
- Number of **attendees** in dissemination and training events (Blue-Cloud 2026 Hackathon, Blue-Cloud 2026 webinar, Workbenches presentations during conferences)
- Number of **references** to the Workbenches in publications including:
 - **EOV/EBV dataset & climatologies publication** on dataset journals
 - **Workflow publication** on Journal of Data Science and Analytics

- Number of views or **downloads of DOIs** published on Seanoe (data), Zenodo (documentation)
- Number of **citations** (from DOIs) in the literature (scientific articles, regional sea reports, etc.)
- Number of **reuse** of Blue-Cloud 2026 Workbenches in other projects

The **success targets** are:

- +20 attendees in each dissemination & training event
- At least one scientific publication on each EOJ & EBV dataset
- Long-term use of Blue-Cloud 2026 Workbenches in other projects

The target number of users, access and views will be defined as an overall target for the Blue-Cloud VRE in the Blue-Cloud 2026 Exploitation Plan.

6.2. KER#3 specific KPI and Targets (2026-2030)

Since WB3 has specific exploitation measures, the following KPIs and success targets applies in addition to the one mentioned above:

- Number of **views of joint policy-brief** with IUCN
- Number of **participants** (early career researchers & established researchers) in **workshops** and **summer schools** (joint AtlantECO-BiOceans5D-BlueCloud SDM workshop, AtlantECO & SynSS summer schools)
- Number of **students** attending courses & downloading training material
- Number of **scientific papers** & joint **collaborations** with other research projects

The **success targets** are:

- +100 views of the joint IUCN policy-brief per month during at least one month
- +20 participants in joint workshops and summer schools
- +20 students attending ETH courses 'Climate Innovation CAS' & 'Biogeochemical Modelling of Sediments, Lakes and Oceans', +20 downloads of practical from marinettraining.eu, at least 2 BSc and MSc projects in species distribution modelling
- 2 scientific papers, 5-10 joint collaborations

7. Joint opportunities for exploitation with other Blue-Cloud KERs

The Workbenches aim to enhance reference datasets from European Blue Data Infrastructures and global initiatives with additional quality control and assessment and extended coverage. The resulting consistent and interoperable EOVS & EBV datasets are valuable to other key components of Blue-Cloud 2026, and are the object of cross-fertilization activities within the project. These activities are facilitated by the shared environment on Blue-Cloud infrastructure. The joint opportunities for exploitation arising from these efforts are outlined below.

7.1. Joint exploitation across Blue-Cloud Workbenches

WB3 leverages a diverse array of data sources as input for its species distribution modelling pipeline, including harmonized, pre-computed and qualified environmental climatologies. The potential to integrate output data products produced by WB1 & 2 as highly qualified sources for the CEPHALOPOD pipeline is being explored, particularly in relation to temperature and nutrients fields.

To build their workflow, the Workbenches are deploying data processing, visualization and analytical tools on the Blue-Cloud VRE, increasing their interoperability with other VRE components and their readiness level. Two of these components are shared by WB1 & 2, being integrated in their workflows to enable swift duplicate checks, quality control and data visualization (webODV, CloneWars). In addition, webODV is also being considered by WB3 to serve non-expert users in the form of a user-friendly and interactive visualization tool for the CEPHALOPOD outputs.

7.2. Joint exploitation with Blue-Cloud Vlabs

Within the Blue-Cloud2026 project, five innovative data processing and analytical services are being developed in the form of Virtual Laboratories (VLabs), demonstrating cross-domain based open science. These key KERs address a range of scientific challenges, providing valuable insights into coastal observations and currents, carbon-plankton dynamics, marine environmental indicators and global fisheries.

Through the Blue-Cloud infrastructure, they can act as initial users of the Workbenches outputs, demonstrating their added-value in speeding up the marine data value chain.

A notable example is the joint exploitation with VLab 4 “Marine Environmental Indicators”. Through joint efforts under WP3 & WP4, WB2 Eutrophication EOVS dataset will be utilized to compute climatologies as inputs to estimate the trophic state index indicator, while the WB1 Temperature & Salinity EOVS dataset will support the derivation of Ocean Heat Content estimates. These outputs will feed into VLab 4

application to monitor and assess the environmental status of marine areas. This collaboration is further described in *D7.2 – Vlabs Individual Exploitation Plans*, Chapter 9.2, p.60.

In the coming months, potential exploitation opportunities between Workbenches and Vlabs will be further explored, seeking to unlock more exploitation uses (i.e. WB3 species distribution maps as interest for Global Fisheries, etc.).

8. Conclusion

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project represents a transformative step in leveraging data-intensive technologies to address critical marine challenges. Through the development of three advanced **Workbenches** targeting physical (Temperature, Salinity), eutrophication (Chlorophyll, Nutrients, Oxygen), and ecosystem-level (Plankton biodiversity and biomass) EOVS & EBVs, the project supports innovative tools facilitating the qualification of datasets essential for assessing the state of the marine environment and the understanding of oceanic systems.

This deliverable outlines **detailed exploitation plans** for each workbench, highlighting the diversity of target users that will benefit from the Workbenches results and the strategic measures designed to ensure their **widespread adoption and impact**. By integrating the Workbenches into the **Blue-Cloud VRE** and aligning with key European and international initiatives, such as **EOSC**, **EDITO**, **EMODnet**, and **CMEMS**, Blue-Cloud 2026 ensures the accessibility, reusability, and relevance of the Workbenches outputs to a broad audience, including **scientists, data modelers, policymakers, Blue Economy stakeholders, and citizens**.

The Workbenches operational uptake and long-term impact are further secured through the active involvement of **BDI** and **European Data Aggregators** experts in the Workbench design, and through the multiple synergies and collaborations being developed with other **European research projects**. Dissemination activities, scientific publications & targeted training will help expand the user base and foster easy adoption in the **research and education sectors**.

Finally, this deliverable also emphasizes the importance of **sustained engagement** of the different stakeholders beyond the project's conclusion, necessary for the Workbenches results to achieve a high and lasting impact by tailoring data products requirements to the emerging societal needs, and optimizing data workflows to meet evolving demands.

This deliverable brings a rich contribution to inform the **Blue-Cloud 2026 Exploitation Plan** and Blue-Cloud 2026 **Sustainability Strategy**, laying the foundation for maximizing the potential of the Workbenches to enhance marine data use and drive sustainable impact.